

GS 79
SPHINX
June 26, 1979

Burn Line in gypsum fill of cuttings and on bedrock floor - R4

When I brushed off the old exposed N balk section of R4, Ns 78, there showed a definite scorched burn line of black from burnt gypsum, about where the cut line of ~~R10~~ R10 begins. Where this black burn line touched the bedrock, there showed a reddish ~~color~~ color as though the bedrock was scorched. But the black burn line continued level across the fill of a depression (Fd2) with more white gypsum under it to the bedrock bottom of the depression, rather than ~~following~~ following the slope of the depression. This was photographed and will be drawn.

Subsequently, it was noticed that the bottoms of the depressions cuttings and holes (Fc17, Fh5) not cleared last year, showed the same reddening of the limestone. This was noted last year when most of the depressions and cuttings were cleared out in the removal R4. The reddening seems to disappear over time, as it no longer shows in most of the cuttings - and in fact may disappear rapidly as it seemed to begin to fade in the newly cleared Fc17, for example.